

3 New Names in *Albuca*, *Garcinia* and *Scutellaria*

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Abstract—Names are proposed for three taxa that lack a legitimate name at their currently accepted taxonomic position.

Albuca somersetianum auctt. ex M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. nov.** ≡ *Albuca exuviata* Baker (in Fl. Cap. (Harvey) 6(3): 456. 1897), nom. illeg., non *Albuca exuviata* (Jacq.) Ker Gawl. (1805).

Garcinia pluvialis auctt. ex M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. nov.** ≡ *Ochrocarpos ambrensis* H.Perrier (in Mém. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat. n.s., xxiv. 107. 1948), non *Garcinia ambrensis* (H.Perrier) P.W.Sweeney & Z.S.Rogers (2008).

Scutellaria dombeyi auctt. ex M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. nov.** ≡ *Perilomia tomentosa* Benth. (in Labiat. Gen. Spec. 446. 1834) ≡ *Scutellaria tomentosa* (Benth.) Epling (1936), nom. illeg., non *Scutellaria tomentosa* Bertol. (1843).

